

THE CONCEPT DEMONSTRATOR PROGRAM OF THE “R&D FOR SMART MATERIALS AND STRUCTURES SYSTEM” PROJECT IN JAPAN

Takao Miyazaki

R&D Center of Smart Materials and Structures System, R&D Institute of Metals and Composites for Future Industries(RIMCOF), Tokyo, Japan

SUMMARY: The “R&D for Smart Materials and Structures System” project has proceeded since late 1998 as the five years program, being supported by NEDO(New Energy and Industrial Technology Development Organization). The project is the Academic Institutions Centered Program, namely, one of collaborated research and development among universities, industries and national laboratories. At first, it consisted of four sub-themes which were 1) Health Monitoring, 2) Active Adaptive Structures, 3) Smart manufacturing, and 4) Actuator Materials and Devices. In early 2000 the Concept Demonstrator Program was added to the project. It is aimed at evaluating what extent each research and development items of sub-themes will attain their targets and establishing common basic technologies for a future “ Smart Structures System”.

The Concept Demonstrator is focused on a aircraft fuselage of the composite structures and designed to integrate each research and development results into it. Two demonstrators are going to be produced. The one is aimed at Damage Detection and Damage Suppression, and the other one is Noise and Vibration Reduction.

KEYWORDS: Smart Materials and Structures, Composite Structures, Damage Detection, Damage Suppression, Noise and Vibration Reduction

INTRODUCTION

The NEDO’s “ R&D for Smart Materials and Structures” project in Japan is now the height of research and development activities. It is the collaborated research and development among universities, industries and national laboratories. Seven universities, seventeen companies and four national laboratories take part in the project. RIMCOF(R&D Institute of Metals and Composites for Future Industries) is the management office of the project. The project includes the above four sub-themes and the Concept Demonstrator Program. Four sub-themes are mainly basic element level research and development and the Concept Demonstrator is actual application-oriented one. The organization of the project is shown in Fig.1.

Fig. 1 Organization of the project

The Concept Demonstrator is designed so as to integrate research and development results of four sub-themes. Of course, we could not make use of results at the start point of the project. Therefore we started the preliminary design of the Concept Demonstrator two years later after research and development of four sub-themes started.

SELECTION OF DEMONSTRATION THEMES

Before starting the preliminary design, we discussed what themes served the purpose of the Concept Demonstrator Program. At first, we asked joined members for submission of demonstration theme proposal. Over thirteen proposals were submitted, but it was difficult to include all of them into one or two demonstrators. So, we decided to select demonstration themes in accordance with the followings criteria, namely,

- 1) Is the theme advanced technology ?
- 2) Do users need the theme for future fuselage structures of a aircraft ?
- 3) Is it possible to show results of research and development on the demonstrator ?
- 4) Is it appropriate to schedule of the project ?

Finally seven themes were selected. They are classified into the followings categories and

shown in Table 1. They are also divided into two groups as upper level, that is,

- (1) Damage Detection and Damage Suppression ↔ Demonstration Theme #1 - #6
- (2) Noise and Vibration Reduction ↔ Demonstration Theme #7

#	Demonstration Categories	Demonstration Themes
1	Real Time Detection of Impact Damage	Optical Fiber Sensors Embedded into CFRP Laminated Structures
2		Integrated Acoustic Emission Sensor Network Systems
3	Damage Detection	Strain Distribution Measurement in Wide Area Using Distributed BOTDR ^{*1} sensors
4		Damage Detection Sensors Using Conductivity of Carbon Fiber(Smart Patch)
5	Damage Suppression	Damage Suppression System Using Embedded SMA(Shape Memory Alloy) Foils
6	Smart manufacturing	Smart Manufacturing on Low Cost Integrated Panel by RTM(Resin Transfer Molding)
7	Noise and Vibration Reduction	Noise and Vibration Reduction Technology in Aircraft Internal Cabin

*1 Brillouin Optical Time Domain Reflectometry

Table 1. Demonstration Themes

CONCEPTS OF DEMONSTRATORS

As mentioned in the summary, the demonstrator is focused on aircraft fuselage. Although it is desirable to test full size fuselage in the view of actual demonstration, it is expensive and takes long time in design and production. Moreover, it needs wide space and a lot of test and measurement facilities. On the other hand, it is difficult for a small demonstrator to simulate primary physical parameters to full scale fuselage due to minimum gauge of materials and standard parts(bolts, nuts, rivets and so on). Stress and strain are key parameters for demonstration theme #1 - #6 of Table 1(Damage Detection and Damage Suppression) and natural frequencies for #7(Noise and Vibration Reduction). As a results of trade-off study, we decided the diameter of 1.5 m(approximately 1/3-scaled size of a small class jetliner).

It is impossible for 1/3-scaled demonstrator to simulate both parameters of stress/strain and natural frequencies simultaneously and, moreover, it is difficult for only one demonstrator to finish demonstration test within period of limited schedule. Consequently we decided to product two demonstrators. The one is aimed at Damage Detection and Damage Suppression which demonstrate #1 through #6 of Table 1, the other one is Noise and Vibration Reduction which demonstrate #7 of Table 1. Structures of demonstrators are mainly composites, but non-influenced parts for physical parameters and outward appearance are metals due to

development cost reduction. Because of simulating a aircraft fuselage, inner pressure is loaded in addition to external bending moment for the Damage Detection and Damage Suppression Demonstrator. For the Noise and Vibration Reduction Demonstrator is excited by speakers and/or shakers externally without bending moment and inner pressure. Image of both demonstrators are shown in Fig.2 and Fig.3 respectively.

Fig.2 Image of “Damage Detection and Damage Suppression Demonstrator”

Fig.3 Image of “Noise and Vibration Reduction Demonstrator”

DAMAGE DETECTION & DAMAGE SUPPRESSION DEMONSTRATOR

Maximum strain of 5000 micron is needed for Damage Detection and Damage Suppression Demonstrator Test. In view of loading facilities capabilities and demonstrator size, 3m is selected as the length of the demonstrator. The demonstrator is supported by cantilever style to the test fixture. At the other side, loading units are attached to the demonstrator through the end cap fitting as shown in Fig.2. The test fixture is assembled around the demonstrator and its size is length: 7m, width: 5m, height: 6m approximately. In addition to the test fixture there are also measurement instruments, air compressor system for inner pressure, controller system and hydraulic units for external bending moment and so on. Then, total space is estimated approximately as length:16 m, width:12m, height: 8m. as shown in Fig.4.

Fig. 4 Overview of demonstrator test area

Test cases are composed of

- 1) strain survey: static strain and deflection measurement \Leftrightarrow about 300 channels.
- 2) repeated loading and unloading test: dynamic strain and deflection measurement \Leftrightarrow about 11 channels
- 3) impulse test: impulse position and/or damage area measurement \Leftrightarrow ultrasonic inspection

And test sequences are shown in Fig. 5.

Fig.5 Test sequences

In Fig.5, “inspection” means 1) crack, deformation and other damages by visual inspection, 2) propagation of initial damages(including artificial defects), and in “final inspection”, local tear down inspection is also included in individual demonstration theme as necessary.

In the preliminary design phase, contents of each demonstration theme also have been studied. They are clarification of demonstration theme target, position and items of evaluation, test procedures, dimension and ply composition of demonstration panels, sensors and wire harness placement, interfaces among each components, validation methods for targets of research and development, and so on. These results have been summed up in the “Preliminary Design Report and drawings”. As examples, overviews of test method in “Integrated AE(Acoustic Emission) Sensor Network Systems” and “Strain Distribution Measurement in Wide Area Using Distributed BOTDR Sensors” are shown in Fig.6 and Fig.7 respectively.

Fig. 6 Demonstration Overview of Integrated AE Sensors Network Systems

Fig. 7 Demonstration overview of Strain Distribution Measurement in Wide Area Using Distributed BOTDR Sensors

Structure of the demonstrator has also been studied in the preliminary design phase. Three basic structural modes can be considered in composite structures as well as metal, mainly, 1) skin-stringer, 2) honeycomb sandwich, 3) monocoque. Monocoque structure is simple, but thick and heavy due to preventing from buckling. Honeycomb sandwich structure starts to be used for business jet aircraft, but it is difficult to connect sub-assemblies of fuselage. Skin-stringer structure is popular one in present jet liner and it is easy to embed sensors/actuators into skin because of thicker skin than face plate of honeycomb sandwich structure. Therefore skin-stringer structure is selected for the demonstrator.

Six demonstration themes of “ Damage Detection and Damage Suppression” are tested in one demonstrator and each theme is assigned position to be tested. Some themes need skin panels into which optical fiber sensors are embedded, and another theme needs other skin panel into which shape memory alloy foils are embedded. So skin panels are divided into four in circumference, that is, upper skin panel, side panel skins and lower skin panel. Moreover,

upper skin panel is divided into two pieces and lower skin panel into three due to production problem. Overview of the demonstrator structures and examples of skin panel connection are shown in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8 Over view of demonstrator and examples of skin panel connection

NOISE AND VIBRATION REDUCTION DEMONSTRATOR

Acoustic absorption materials have good noise reduction features in high frequency range. But, in low frequency range, they need thick absorption layers in order to reduce noise level significantly. Therefore, it is practical solution to use active noise control in low frequency range and acoustic absorption materials in high frequency range. In Noise and Vibration Reduction Demonstrator, target is frequency range below 500Hz.

The demonstrator is the same size as the Damage Detection and Damage Suppression Demonstrator as mentioned in “Concepts of Demonstrators”. Skin panel thickness, dimension of stringers and frames and spaces between the stringers as well as the frames of the Noise and Vibration Reduction Demonstrator are different from the Damage Detection and Damage Suppression Demonstrator due to differences of key parameters to be simulated. In this demonstrator natural frequencies are key parameters to be simulated. All natural frequencies of the demonstrator can not meet those of the assumed jet liner. Therefore our

policies to placement of natural frequencies are the followings.

- 1) to meet approximately natural frequencies of panel one bay enclosed by stringers and frames
- 2) to meet order of structural vibration natural frequencies and acoustic vibration natural frequencies

In accordance with the above policies, dimension of stringers and frames, space of them and shape of end caps are designed. Structural-acoustic coupled mode analysis results are shown in Fig. 9 for first three modes.

Fig. 9 Results of structural-acoustic coupled vibration analysis (the first 3 modes)

High performance PZT sensors and actuators which are developed by “Actuator Materials and Devices” group are supposed to be used. Both are same size of length : 30mm (circumference direction), length : 40mm(axial direction) , thickness : 0.5mm and curvature : 750mm. Placement of sensors and actuators will be decided, based on results of future simulation.

Even if frequency range is limited below 500 Hz, there are many natural frequencies in the demonstrator as shown in Fig. 10. Because it is impossible to control all frequencies, we have to find the most efficient frequencies to reduce noise and vibration level.

Numbers of Natural Frequencies

Fig. 10 Natural frequencies of the demonstrator

CONCLUSION

The NEDO’s “R&D for Smart Materials and Structures” project just finished the third year of five years program. From now on the project is focused on two demonstrators{ 1}Damage Detection and Damage Suppression and 2} Noise and Vibration Reduction} program. In the fourth year(FY2001) both demonstrator will finish detail design and start production of parts/sub-assembly. Moreover, the Noise and Vibration Reduction Demonstrator will finish final assembly and start vibration characteristics acquisition test. In the last year(FY2002) the Damage Detection and Damage Suppression Demonstrator will finish final assembly and start test. Both demonstrator will finish test on March 2003.